

Effect of harvest time, drying, and length of storage on uric acid content of milled rice. Ludhiana, India.

Variety	Harvest time	Uric acid content (mg/100 g)							
		Without drying				With drying			
		1 mo	6 mo	12 mo	Mean	1 mo	6 mo	12 mo	Mean
IR8	Early	4.13	8.64	10.50	7.76	3.75	9.00	9.00	7.25
	Normal	4.13	8.63	9.75	7.50	3.38	9.00	9.00	7.13
	Late	3.75	8.62	9.00	7.12	3.75	8.25	8.63	6.88
	Mean	4.00	8.63	9.75	7.46	3.63	8.75	8.88	7.09
PR108	Early	5.25	7.88	9.38	7.50	3.76	6.00	9.38	6.38
	Normal	4.50	7.50	9.00	7.00	3.75	6.38	7.50	5.88
	Late	4.50	6.75	10.13	7.13	3.74	6.75	7.50	6.00
	Mean	4.75	7.38	9.50	7.21	3.75	6.38	8.13	6.09
Basmati 370	Early	3.75	4.50	7.13	5.13	3.75	6.00	6.75	5.50
	Normal	4.88	6.75	7.13	6.25	3.75	6.00	7.13	5.63
	Late	4.50	6.00	6.38	5.63	3.38	5.63	6.00	5.00
	Mean	4.38	5.75	6.88	5.67	3.63	5.88	6.63	5.38

LSD (0.05) Harvest time = ns. Drying = 0.30.
Storage time = 0.36. Varieties = 0.36.

storage and was higher in samples stored without drying.

IR8 had higher uric acid content than PR108 and Basmati 370.

The predominant insect species found were *Corcyra cephalonica*, *Sitophilus oryzae*, and *Sitotroga cerealella*. □

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Farming systems

Establishing wheat with minimal tillage and irrigation after rice

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We grew rice - wheat - jute in a 2-yr field experiment 1983-85 in a low-lying field. IR579 rice (120 d duration) was grown in both wet seasons, direct seeded and transplanted, with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha. UP-262 wheat (120 d duration) was grown with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha immediately after rice (mid-Nov) with two levels of irrigation and four levels of tillage. Rupali jute (90 d duration for fiber) was sown in mid-Apr with 50-25-25 kg NPK/ha and fiber was measured the third wk of Jun for direct seeded rice and Jul for transplanted rice.

The experiment was laid out in a split-split-plot design, with rice in the main plot, irrigated wheat in the subplot, and wheat tillage after rice in the sub-subplot, with four replications. The soil of the experimental site (22.39° N, 88.54° E) was alluvial, with 0.55%

Effect of rice planting method, irrigation, and tillage in wheat after rice on yields of rice, wheat, and jute in West Bengal, India, 1983-85.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)			
	Rice ^a	Wheat	Jute	Total
<i>Rice planting method</i>				
Broadcast	1.8	2.8	0.7	5.3
Transplanted	2.4	2.2	0.8	5.4
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	
<i>Tillage^b for wheat after rice</i>				
No tillage	2.9	2.0	0.7	5.6
Minimum tillage	2.9	2.6	0.8	6.3
Normal tillage	3.0	2.8	0.7	6.5
Irrigation + normal tillage	2.9	2.4	0.7	6.1
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	
<i>Irrigation in wheat</i>				
At crown root initiation + flowering	3.1	2.4	0.8	6.3
At crown root initiation, late tillering, flowering, milk stage	2.8	2.5	0.7	6.0
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	-

^a Av of 2 yr. ^b No tillage = soil between rice rows opened with hand-drawn tine. Minimum tillage = 2 plowings with bullock, lengthwise and crosswise, followed by laddering. Normal tillage = 4 plowings with bullock, lengthwise and crosswise, followed by laddering.

organic C, 16 kg P/ha, 21 kg K/ha, and pH 6.9.

Broadcast and transplanted rice yields did not significantly differ (see table).

The cumulative effect of tillage and irrigation in wheat also did not significantly affect rice yield.

Wheat grain yields after rice, rice planting method, tillage operation, and irrigation did not differ significantly.

Jute fiber yield did not differ significantly with tillage and irrigation in preceding wheat.

In total production, transplanted rice was better than direct seeded. Four plowings and two plowings were equally good for wheat, but two irrigations were better than four irrigations. □

A rice-based intercropping sequence for Vindhyan red loam soils of eastern Uttar Pradesh

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Potential annual yield of crops on well-drained Vindhyan red soils (based on water availability and soil waterholding capacity) is estimated at 2-4 t/ha. But actual production is only 0.5-1 t/ha. The wet season is the main cropping season and upland rice occupies most of the area.